
54. Animations, stereos and fly-throughs

ASTROMETRY, EVEN SPACE ASTROMETRY, doesn't necessarily easily lend itself to 'public outreach'.

The results of the first space mission, Hipparcos, was a catalogue of 120,000 star positions, parallaxes and proper motions. In printed form, the main catalogue ran to five volumes, more than 2000 pages of small densely packed type, superficially reminiscent of an old (printed) telephone directory. Astronomers made extensive use of the information; but in terms of visual impact, and popular appeal, Hipparcos couldn't complete with, say, the stunning images of deep space returned in glorious abundance by the Hubble Space Telescope.

And while scientists were, even in 1997 and more so today, encouraged to make the results of these ambitious space missions accessible to the wider public who, through their taxes, essentially sponsor them, the task was and remains a challenging one.

In 2009 I wrote a popular account of the Hipparcos mission under the title *'The Making of History's Star Map'*, published by Springer. A more mainstream publisher came rather close to accepting it, but eventually declined because 'two thirds of our sales in English are sold in the US, and the US public has not heard of Hipparcos'. I argued, unsuccessfully, that surely the purpose of writing a popular book was to make things known to those who had never encountered the subject before.

Curiously, I was invited instead to write a general book on the Hubble Space Telescope! The fact that I had no inside knowledge of the project, and that there were already more than 30 published titles on it, were not seen as impediments to this offer... which I declined.

AN INVITATION TO DELIVER the annual Darwin Lecture to the UK Royal Astronomical Society back in 1997 was an ideal opportunity to try for some special visualisation of the mission results. It is not easy, today, to comprehend the more primitive state of digital projection just two decades ago. So my lecture centred, precariously, around 35-mm stereo slide pairs, synchronously projected, and suitably imaged, through two identical slide projectors equipped with orthogonal polarising fil-

ters. Projected onto a large silvered screen to avoid loss of polarisation, with the audience equipped with appropriately polarised glasses, I displayed a series of star fields in their full stereoscopic glory.

The impact of Hipparcos, aided by this son-et-lumière performance, led to my Invited Discourse at the IAU General Assembly in 2000, with the stereoscopic system scaled up to hefty high-powered twin projectors, and my first efforts at including stereo videos for an audience of 1200 in Manchester's huge Bridgewater Hall. In a darkened auditorium, the effect is almost like looking up at the night sky, while resolving the depths of space. It is powerful visually, but laborious to replicate.

And an anecdote: during my preparation for this talk, which required a bulk order of cardboard-framed polarised 'glasses' from a supplier in London, my telephone enquiry was interrupted by the assistant as I was explaining my intentions. *'Let me stop you there'*, he said, *'I'm an amateur astronomer, and stars are just too far away for any stereo effect to be observable'*. After a short pause, I explained why I thought I could. *Ah!*, he said, *there's probably just one person in the world in a position to demonstrate this effect, and I'm speaking to them!*

THERE ARE VARIOUS REASONS why polarised light projection is particularly effective in displaying stereoscopic scenes. One important advantage is that the subtleties of the slightly different star colours can also be used, which aids the brain in more easily grasping the stereoscopic effect. Anaglyph (e.g. red-green) images can also work, but are considerably less forceful.

Another technique which is quite reasonable in visualising the stereoscopic effect of star fields is 'swing stereoscopy', in which two lateral projections (or a more complete video sequence), are cycled repeatedly. I will refer to a couple of examples of this below.

A further engaging technique for visualising the 3d structure of interplanetary, interstellar, or intergalactic space (and enabled by today's computational and projection technology) are simulated fly-throughs. Again, I will refer to some spectacular examples below.

AS WELL AS THEIR STEREOSCOPIC DISTANCES, Hipparcos and Gaia also measure the *motions* of stars through space. These motions, suitably ‘speeded up’ and extrapolated over thousands of years, can then be compressed into just a few seconds of movie time.

We can then see things like the configuration of stars in the night sky as they will appear thousands of years in the future. As just one example, the easily recognisable constellation of Ursa Major will look very different, far in the future, compared to how it appears to us today.

TO ILLUSTRATE THE principles, elsewhere on my www site I’ve included some animations based on the Hipparcos results for both the Hyades and Pleiades open star clusters. Each covers a sky region of $8^\circ \times 6^\circ$, each reconstructing the star magnitudes, colours, distances, and space motions. In the first of each series, star motions are extrapolated — over 60 000 years for the Hyades, and 150 000 years for the Pleiades.

In the second, star distances are visualised by ‘swing stereoscopy’ by changing the observer’s effective location (and corresponding to the Earth’s annual motion around the Sun).

In the third sequence, the two effects are combined to show the (amplified) annual parallax superimposed on the space motion.

The continuous variations in the relative positions of the stars with time illustrates the principles used by Hipparcos and Gaia in determining (and decoupling) stellar distances and space motions.

A MOVIE ILLUSTRATING the Gaia proper motions, created by Jacqueline Faherty of the American Museum of Natural History, shows the Gaia stars (from DR2) within 200 parsec of the Sun. The animation runs over 1.5 million years, with the star motions at 25 000-year time steps compressed into 1 second of movie time:

www.youtube.com/watch?v=qBZKXwpzdDw

Within this vast local volume, we can see star clusters moving slowly through space. And we can see fast-moving stars racing across the field, members of our Galaxy’s halo population passing through our neighbourhood. Some of her other animations are at:

www.dropbox.com/sh/

[4v21ane28d6gd2x/AADJHaMG1Fu6RJGDksjBxw0Ga?dl=0](https://www.dropbox.com/sh/4v21ane28d6gd2x/AADJHaMG1Fu6RJGDksjBxw0Ga?dl=0)

Jackie Faherty received the American Astronomical Society’s 2020 Vera Rubin Early Career Award for her work on the kinematics of very faint stars in our Galaxy, and for ‘developing unique ways to engage the public and professional science teams in astrometry’. In one of ESA’s ‘soundbite’ videos, she describes Gaia as: ... *one of humanity’s greatest missions... a story of vast proportions in our understanding of how stars form and evolve.*

A FIRST DETAILED scientific assessment of what Gaia is contributing to our knowledge of stars within 100 pc was published in December 2020 (Smart et al., 2021), using the data from Early Data Release 3 (EDR3), which I have described in some detail in my essay #33. The authors also provided some information graphics and videos, which are collected at:

www.cosmos.esa.int/web/gaia/edr3-gcns

Amongst these are a fly-through of more than 300 000 stars based on this Gaia Catalogue of Nearby Stars:

www.youtube.com/watch?v=bzQUNClE53o

and the Galactic orbits of a subsample of 74 281 stars:

www.youtube.com/watch?v=k9pHGhNtyPk

AN EXTENSIVE SUITE OF Gaia star animations is the A ‘3D Universe Simulator’, comprising more than a billion objects, and made available by Stefan Jordan and colleagues in the Gaia group of the Astronomisches Rechen-Institut (ZAH, University of Heidelberg):

zah.uni-heidelberg.de/gaia/outreach/gaiasky

Amongst its many capabilities are the ability to navigate freely through the Galaxy, and its support for various forms of stereoscopic projection.

AMONGST VARIOUS OTHER Gaia animations now publicly available, or in preparation, are a series of nice maps and interactive tools created by Kevin Jardine. These provide the possibility to fly through the catalogue, searching for some chosen star, or simply clicking on a star to find its name and properties:

galaxymap.org/drupal/blog/1

I WILL FINISH WITH two movies that are completely independent of Gaia and space astrometry, but which provide an important cosmological context.

The first is the acclaimed Millennium Simulations of Volker Springel and colleagues, from 2005:

wwwmpa.mpa-garching.mpg.de/galform/millennium

Based on more than 10 billion interacting particles, it shows the dark matter distribution in the Universe today. It highlights structure on scales, ranging from several billion parsecs down to substructures as small as 10 kpc. It encapsulates our understanding of how galaxies, including our own, have formed.

The second is a simulation of disk galaxy formation, from the cosmological N-body simulations TNG50, also created by Volker Springel and colleagues, which zooms in on the formation, over billions of years, of a disk galaxy very closely resembling our own:

www.tng-project.org/media

THE POINT to stress here is how well these simulations, which are based on extensive physical *models* of our Universe’s formation, now resemble the sort of structure that Gaia is discovering in our own Galaxy. With Gaia, astrometry is truly confronting cosmology.

